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Sheep feeding preference and methane mitigation potential of fodder tree leaves in the Sahelian silvopastoral zone of Senegal

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ABSTRACT

Feed scarcity during the long dry season is a major constraint to live-stock production in the Sahel. During this period, fodder trees provide a valuable source of nutrients. This study assessed sheep feeding preferences for five woody species from Senegal's silvopastoral zone (*Adansonia digitata*, *Acacia tortilis* subsp. *raddiana*, *Balanites aegyptiaca*, *Guiera senegalensis*, *Khaya senegalensis*) and evaluated their enteric methane mitigation potential. A cafeteria-style trial quantified voluntary intake, feeding time and preference coefficients of four sheep for fresh and air-dried leaves over 5 consecutive days during daily 30-min sessions. *In vitro* gas production assays, conducted with and without polyethylene glycol (PEG), measured total gas, methane concentration, and estimated digestibility. Leaves of *A. raddiana* and *B. aegyptiaca* showed high crude protein contents (168.7 and 167.0 g/kg DM) and metabolisable energy values (8.7 and 12.1 MJ/kg DM). In contrast, *G. senegalensis* and *K. senegalensis* contained high fibre (aNDF: 586.6 and 484.8 g/kg DM) and condensed tannins (35.8 and 66.9 g/kg DM). PEG addition increased gas production in *A. raddiana*, *G. senegalensis* and *K. senegalensis*, confirming tannin inhibition of fermentation. Sheep showed a clear preference ($p < 0.001$) for ingesting fresh *A. raddiana* (298 g/animal) and *B. aegyptiaca* (270 g/animal) leaves; feeding time and preference coefficients followed the same pattern. Preference coefficients were positively associated with crude protein and negatively linked to fibre and tannin contents, while tannin-rich species also produced less methane *in vitro*. Overall, *A. raddiana* and *B. aegyptiaca* emerged as valuable indigenous fodder resources for improving dry-season nutrition and potentially contributing to climate-smart livestock systems in the West African Sahel.

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1. Introduction

In semi-arid and arid regions worldwide, tree leaves and woody legumes provide a sustainable supplement to low-quality forages – enhancing ruminant nutrition during

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periods of scarcity, reducing dependence on purchased feeds, and supporting climate-smart livestock practices (Vandermeulen et al. 2018). Their integration into ruminant diets contributes to feed-resource diversification and strengthens the resilience of small-holder systems facing seasonal feed shortages (Amole et al. 2022). The prolonged dry season in the Sahelian zone of West Africa leads to a rapid decline in available herbaceous biomass and an increase in their structural cell wall components, such as cellulose and lignin, which results in poor forage quality and reduced feed intake in ruminants (Lo et al. 2022). Fodder trees and shrubs represent an important alternative feed resource during this period, as their leaves generally retain higher crude protein concentrations and contain bioactive secondary metabolites that may influence rumen fermentation (Franzel et al. 2014). Among these metabolites, condensed tannins have received particular attention due to their dual effects: at moderate levels, they may modulate rumen fermentation and reduce enteric methane formation, while high concentrations can decrease feed intake and nutrient digestibility (Jayanegara et al. 2009; Cardoso-Gutierrez et al. 2021).

Despite the widespread use of woody species by livestock keepers in the Sahel, scientific information on their nutritional value, palatability and fermentation characteristics remains limited, especially for species native to the West African silvopastoral zone (Amole et al. 2022). Understanding how leaf chemical composition, particularly crude protein, fibre fractions, and tannins, relates to intake and fermentation responses is essential for their effective use in ruminant diets. This study therefore combined a controlled cafeteria-style preference test with *in vitro* gas production assays, with and without polyethylene glycol (PEG), to quantify voluntary intake, preference indices and fermentation characteristics of selected woody species. Based on an exploratory survey with livestock keepers, five frequently cited woody species were selected: *Acacia tortilis* subsp. *raddiana*, *Adansonia digitata*, *Balanites aegyptiaca*, *Guiera senegalensis* and *Khaya senegalensis* (Beye et al. 2026). These species exhibit contrasting nutritional profiles, ranging from protein-rich (*A. raddiana*, *B. aegyptiaca*) to tannin- or fibre-rich (*G. senegalensis*, *K. senegalensis*) foliage (Abdulrazak et al. 2000; Coulibaly et al. 2025). Among them, we aimed to identify those woody forages with favourable nutritional and fermentative properties that could contribute to improved dry-season feeding strategies and potentially reduced methane emissions in the semi-arid ruminant production systems of Sahelian countries.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study site

The experiment was conducted in 2021 at the Dahra Animal Production Research Center (CRZ Dahra) in the silvopastoral zone of Senegal (15°21' N, 15°26' W). The area has a Sahelian climate with a mean annual temperature of about 27°C and an average annual rainfall of approximately 370 mm, concentrated between June and October (Delon et al. 2017). The natural vegetation is dominated by shrubs and scattered trees typical of semi-arid rangelands (Diatta et al. 2023).

2.2. Experimental animals and housing

Four male Sahelian *Peulh* sheep (age 12–24 months; body weight 28.2 ± 1.9 kg) were used. Before the start of the experiment, the animals underwent a quarantine period and received routine health treatments, including deworming. Each sheep was housed individually in a pen of 3 m \times 2 m size with a concrete floor situated in a roofed and well-ventilated building. Each pen was equipped with five plastic feeding buckets, one for each tree species tested. Buckets were placed side by side and their positions were rotated daily to avoid positional bias. Clean drinking water and a mineral lick were available *ad libitum*.

2.3. Experimental design and feeding regime

2.3.1. Selection and collection of fodder leaves

A first batch of leaves from the five selected woody species (approximately 3–4 kg of fresh material per species) was harvested between October and November 2021 from 72 trees located around the Dahra Animal Production Research Center. The sampling included 25 trees of *Balanites aegyptiaca*, 18 of *Guiera senegalensis*, 15 of *Acacia tortilis* subsp. *raddiana*, 9 of *Khaya senegalensis* and 5 *Adansonia digitata* trees. Immediately after collection, the leaves were completely homogenised per tree species, spread in thin layers on clean plastic sheets in a well-ventilated shed and turned several times per day to avoid moisture accumulation and fungal growth. At ambient daytime temperatures averaging 28°C and an air humidity below 30% during the study period, air-drying of the leaves required approximately 5 d for the small-sized leaves of *B. aegyptiaca*, *G. senegalensis* and *A. raddiana*, while the larger leaves of *A. digitata* and *K. senegalensis* required about 8 d until they were completely air-dry. Field dryness was assessed through a combination of visual and tactile indicators (absence of surface moisture, non-tacky texture, brittle structure) and by daily monitoring of subsample weights on a portable scale of 0.1 g accuracy. Drying was considered complete when subsample weights remained stable on 2 consecutive days.

Once dried, the leaves were loosely packed in breathable woven polypropylene bags and stored in a shaded, dry and well-ventilated room until their use in the experiment. In addition, fresh leaves (2–3 kg per species and per day) were collected from exactly the same trees per species throughout December 2021. They were kept overnight in a shaded and aerated area to maintain freshness prior to distribution in the cafeteria trial in the following morning.

2.3.2. Structure of the feeding trial

The cafeteria-style preference test (Ben Salem et al. 1997) was conducted from 23 November to 12 December 2021, covering a total of 20 d. The trial comprised four successive phases: a 4-d adaptation period to the setup, a 5-d fresh-leaf testing phase, a 4-d transition period following the same protocol as the adaptation phase, and a 5-d dried-leaf testing phase. The trial was both preceded and followed by a weighing day, during which the animals' initial and final body weights (BW) were recorded after a 12 h overnight fast. An additional intermediate BW measurement was taken at the end of the fresh-leaf testing phase. All body weight measurements were performed using

a suspended electronic scale (Kern & Sohn GmbH, Germany; capacity 99 kg; accuracy 0.05 kg).

2.3.3. Adaptation phase

During the adaptation phase, each sheep was individually familiarised with the test setup, which consisted of five feeding buckets placed in a row in its pen, during a 30-min morning session. All buckets contained the same standard diet, consisting of 200 g air-dry matter of a mixture of dried wild grass (bush hay; 75%) and wheat bran (25%). During the 4-d period, efforts were made to detect and reduce any positional bias the animals might exhibit towards particular bucket locations, as such bias could confound subsequent preference assessments. Accordingly, the positions of the buckets were systematically rotated each day. Observations of the animals' feeding behaviour were conducted daily between 08:00 and 09:15, with animals A and D observed from 08:00 to 08:30 and animals B and C from 08:45 to 09:15. In addition to behavioural observations, the quantities of standard feed offered and refused were weighed before and after each 30-min observation period, to estimate individual 30-min feed intake and ensure that all animals were fully accustomed to the feeding setup, the rotation of bucket positions, and the presence of observers before the testing phase started.

2.3.4. Preference testing with fresh and dried leaves

During both the fresh and dried leaf testing phases, each animal had simultaneous access to the leaves of all five woody species, with each species offered in a separate, clearly labelled feeding bucket placed side by side (Figure 1). To avoid positional bias, the arrangement of the buckets was rotated daily throughout the trial. Every morning, 650 g of fresh leaves or 200 g of air-dried leaves per species were weighed using a tabletop electronic balance (G&G GmbH, Kaarst, Germany; capacity 6 kg; accuracy 0.1 g) and distributed into the corresponding buckets. Based on the leaves' fresh matter content determined during air-drying (see 2.3.1.) and subsequent oven drying (see 2.4.1.), the offered amounts of fresh and dried leaves were adjusted to a consistent dry matter supply across species of approximately 200 g air-dry weight per sheep during the 30-min observation period.

2.3.5. Observation schedule and parameter recording

To ensure accurate monitoring of individual sheep's preference for a particular ligneous foliage under uniform and controlled conditions, feeding behaviour was observed for animals A and D from 08:00 to 08:30 and for animals B and C from 08:45 to 09:15 during each 5-d testing phase with the fresh and the dry leaves, respectively (Figure 1). Behavioural observations and data recording procedures followed established cafeteria-test protocols (Ben Salem et al. 1997) and standard guidelines for feeding behaviour assessment in ruminants (Provenza et al. 2003). Each animal was monitored by a team of two trained observers; the four persons were equipped with stopwatches to record the cumulative eating time devoted to each woody species, whereby any active oral interaction with the leaves through grasping, chewing, or swallowing was considered as feeding. To minimise observer bias, the four persons conducted joint training sessions to standardise the

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the cafeteria-style preference test. Sheep were tested in two consecutive groups of two animals (A and D; B and C), with each one housed in a separate pen and monitored by two trained observers who recorded the feeding time per bucket. During each 30-min morning session, five woody species (Ad, Ac, Ba, Gu, Kh) were offered simultaneously in individual buckets arranged systematically in front of each animal. To avoid positional bias, the buckets' positions (P1–P5) were rotated daily: the species in position 1 moved to position 2, position 2 to position 3, and so forth, with the species in position 5 cycling back to position 1. After 5 d, each species had occupied all five positions once.

identification, classification, and recording of feeding behaviours. Before the trial began, behaviour records for a given animal were cross-checked to ensure consistency and agreement among observers. During the 5-d test periods, the recordings from the two persons assigned to one animal were averaged for the 30-min observation session.

At the end of each daily 30-min test session, leaf refusals were collected and weighed separately for each animal and ligneous species. Individual voluntary intake was calculated as the difference between the quantity of leaves offered and remaining after the observation period. The basal diet of *ad libitum* offered bush hay and 500 g/d of wheat bran (as fed) was distributed in two meals at 09:30 and 15:00, and all leftovers were removed at 18:00. The long overnight fast should ensure that the feeding motivation of sheep A and D, and B and C, respectively, was not influenced by the 45-min interval between the two morning observation sessions (Ben Salem et al. 1997; Coulibaly et al. 2025). No bedding material was used during the preference test to avoid bias from nibbling of straw or sawdust.

2.4. Leaf sampling and laboratory analyses

2.4.1. Feed quality analysis

During the two 5-d experimental phases, samples were collected from all leaf species offered and corresponding leftovers per animal. While for leftovers the total amount was weighed daily and air-dried, a 100 g subsample was taken daily from the fresh or dried leaf material offered. These daily samples were pooled by leaf type, experimental phase, and, for leftovers, animal, and thoroughly homogenised. A representative 100 g aliquot of leftover leaves was kept per animal for dry matter determination only. In a first step, all samples (offer and leftover) were air-dried at ambient temperature (about 28°C, see 2.3.1.), then ground to 1 mm particle size using a Cyclotec mill (Foss analytical, Hamburg, Germany). For the tree leaves offered, only one fully homogenised pool sample that combined air-dried fresh and dried leaves harvested from the same individual trees during the same season (see 2.3.1.) was analysed. Feed quality analyses were performed in duplicate following VDLUFA (2012) methods. Dry matter (DM) was determined by oven-drying the air-dry samples at 105°C for 72 h (Memmert GmbH & Co.KG, Schwabach, Germany) until constant weight was reached (method 3.1). Crude ash (CA) was determined by incinerating samples at 550°C (method 8.1) in a Nabertherm P330 muffle furnace (Nabertherm GmbH Lilienthal, Germany), and organic matter (OM) was calculated by subtracting the ash content from DM. Nitrogen (N) content was determined by the Kjeldahl method (method 4.1.1) using a Vapodest VAP 550s distillation unit (Gerhardt GmbH & Co.KG, Königswinter, Germany), and crude protein (CP) was calculated as $N \times 6.25$. Amylase-treated neutral detergent fibre (aNDF), acid detergent fibre (ADF) and acid detergent lignin (ADL) were analysed sequentially following Van Soest et al. (1991) and using an ANKOM200 fibre analyser (ANKOM Technology, Macedon, NY, USA); for aNDF analysis, samples were treated with heat-stable amylase.

Condensed tannins (CT) were quantified using the butanol-HCl-iron method following the procedure described by Jayanegara et al. (2009). Briefly, 50 µL of the sample extract was mixed with 200 µL of 70% acetone water, 50 µL of iron ammonium reagent, and 1.5 ml of butanol-HCl solution in a glass tube. The mixture was incubated for 60 min at 97°C in a preheated dry block and then cooled to room temperature. Absorbance was read at 550 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Analytik Jena GmbH & Co.KG, Jena, Germany) against a reagent blank. CT concentration was expressed as leucocyanidin equivalents, assuming an absorbance of 460 nm for a 10 mg/ml leucocyanidin standard. All analyses were performed in duplicate and results were corrected for DM content.

Total phenols (TP) were estimated using the Folin–Ciocalteu method adapted for plant extracts (Singleton and Rossi 1965). About 200 mg of ground sample was extracted with 70% aqueous acetone, followed by addition of Folin–Ciocalteu reagent and sodium carbonate. After incubation in a dark chamber at 20°C for 30 min, absorbance was measured at 725 nm and results were expressed as tannic acid equivalents per kg DM (Makkar 2003).

2.4.2. *In vitro* gas production of tree leaves

Using the modified Hohenheim Gas Test (Menke and Steingass 1988; Leberl et al. 2007; VDLUFA 2012), *in vitro* fermentation analyses were carried out from March to May 2022

at the Ruminant Nutrition Laboratory of the University of Göttingen, where at the time only one rumen-fistulated cow, and no rumen-fistulated sheep, was available.

Ground leaf samples (1 mm) were incubated in glass syringes. For the assays without polyethylene glycol (PEG), 0.200 g of sample was used, whereas for the PEG assays, 0.250 g of sample material was combined with 0.450 g of PEG to bind CT (Besharati 2017). Each syringe received 30 ml of buffered rumen fluid prepared with 33 g/L sodium bicarbonate and 6 g/L ammonium bicarbonate which followed the protocol of Menke and Steingass (1988). The donor cow received a standardised diet comprising 75% grass hay and 25% wheat bran-based concentrate (as fed). Rumen fluid was used unfiltered; syringes and glass bottles were pre-warmed to 37.8°C for 2 h and flushed with CO₂ to maintain anaerobic conditions before mixing the rumen fluid with the buffer and filling the syringes, respectively. Triplicate incubations were conducted in two runs over 2 separate days, resulting in six replicates per sample and per treatment (with and without PEG). Each run included syringes containing blanks (no substrate), hay standard, concentrate standard, and test samples with and without PEG.

Syringes were incubated at 39°C in a rotary incubator for 24 h. Gas volumes were recorded at 8 h and again at 24 h, with syringe plungers reset to 30 ml at 8 h if necessary. In the case syringes were set back, the total gas produced after 24 h was obtained by summing the gas volumes recorded after 8 and 24 h. At the end of the incubation, the total gas produced by each sample was collected with a gastight syringe and injected into 5.9 ml evacuated Exetainer vials (Labco Ltd., London, UK). The methane concentration (%CH₄) in the headspace gas sample was determined by gas chromatography using a Trace 1300 Gas Chromatograph (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), equipped with a TriPlus RSH autosampler and a TG-BOND Msieve 5A capillary column (30 m × 0.53 mm ID, 50 µm film thickness; Thermo Fisher Scientific). Argon served as the carrier gas. Methane was reported in percent of total gas, whereby values were not corrected for CH₄ release of the blank rumen fluid.

Total gas production (GP) values were corrected by subtracting those of the blank syringes and expressed in millilitres per 200 mg dry matter (DM). The *in vitro* digestibility of organic matter (IVOMD) was calculated using the equation of Menke and Steingass (1988).

$$IVOMD = 15.38 + 0.8453 \times GP + 0.0595 \times CP + 0.0675 \times CA$$

where GP is the gas production (ml/200 mg DM), CP is the crude protein (g/kg DM), and CA is the crude ash (g/kg DM) content.

In vitro metabolisable energy content (IVME, MJ/kg DM) of the leaves was subsequently estimated from IVOMD using the formula of Njidda and Nasiru (2010):

$$IVME = 0.15 + 0.1557 \times IVOMD + 0.0130 \times CA$$

where IVOMD is the *in vitro* digestibility of organic matter and CA is the crude ash (g/kg DM) content.

2.5. Data analysis

All data were first entered in tabular databases and pre-processed using Microsoft Excel 2019, then analysed using R software (version 4.5.0). The analysis was structured around

three main components: nutritional composition of leaves offered (descriptive statistics only), *in vitro* fermentation parameters, and feeding behaviour (30-min leaf intake, 30-min feeding time, and preference coefficient); the nutritional composition of bush hay and wheat bran is not reported here. For the *in vitro* data, the general model was of linear structure:

$$Y = \mu + T + \varepsilon$$

where Y is the response variable, μ the overall mean, T the fixed effect of leaf type, leaf state (fresh/dry), or PEG addition, respectively, and ε the residual error term.

Feeding behaviour data were analysed using linear mixed-effects models to account for repeated measurements on the same animal across experimental days. Tree species (Spec) and leaf status (Stat, i.e. fresh or dried) were included as fixed effects, while animal identity (Anim) and experimental day (Day) were included as random effects:

$$Y_{ijkl} = \mu + \text{Spec}_i + \text{Stat}_j + (\text{Anim}_k) + (\text{Day}_l) + \varepsilon_{ijkl}$$

where Y represents the response variable, μ is the overall mean, Spec and Stat are fixed effects, Anim and Day are random effects, and ε is the residual error term.

Analyses were performed in R using the *lme4* and *lmer* test packages. When significant effects were detected, pairwise comparison of species was conducted using estimated marginal means with Tukey adjustment.

In vitro fermentation data were first tested for normality using the *shapiro.test()* function from the *stats* package in R (Royston 1995). As the assumption of normality was not met, comparisons of treatments (with and without PEG: +PEG, -PEG) were conducted separately for each woody species using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test with the *wilcox.test()* function from the *stats* package (Bauer 1972).

Fresh matter (FM) and dry matter (DM) intake of sheep were calculated as the difference between the quantities of leaves offered and left after the daily 30-min observation period. Intake was expressed both in grams per animal and in grams per kilogram BW, using the animals' average BW across the 20 d of experimentation.

Total feeding time (in seconds) was determined by summing the durations of all feeding events per woody species and animal during the daily 30-min observation period.

The preference coefficient (PC) was determined by dividing the quantity of leaves (fresh or dried) consumed from a particular species by the total quantity of leaves consumed across all species.

Normality of intake, feeding time, and preference coefficient data was assessed using the *shapiro.test()* function. Since the data were not normally distributed, comparisons between tree species were performed using the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test (Kruskal and Wallis 1952) with the *kruskal.test()* function from the *stats* package (Hollander et al. 2013). When significant differences were detected ($p < 0.05$), post hoc comparisons were conducted using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction via the *dunnTest()* function from the *FSA* package (Ogle et al. 2023). Boxplots were used to visualise differences between treatments (*in vitro* test only) and species (*in vitro* and preference test), using the *ggplot2* and *ggpubr* packages (Kassambara 2020).

To explore the relationship between forage quality traits and key animal responses, a correlation matrix was computed. The matrix included CP, aNDF, ADF, CT, TP, and

IVOMD as independent variables, and related them to the three dependent variables PC, GP, and %CH₄. Pearson's correlation coefficients were calculated using the *cor()* function from the *stats* package (Becker et al. 1988), and associated *p*-Values were computed using the *cor.mtest()* function from the *corrplot* package (Wei and Simko 2021).

3. Results

3.1. Chemical composition of selected tree leaves

The leaves of the five woody species differed in their chemical composition (Table 1). Dry matter (DM) content was highest in *A. raddiana* (533 g/kg FM) and lowest in *A. digitata* (310 g/kg FM). Organic matter (OM) ranged from 834 g/kg DM in *B. aegyptiaca* to 916 g/kg DM in *K. senegalensis*. Crude protein concentration was highest in *A. raddiana* (169 g/kg DM) and lowest in *G. senegalensis* (110 g/kg DM). With respect to fibre fractions, *G. senegalensis* showed high aNDF and ADF contents (587 and 497 g/kg DM, respectively), whereas *B. aegyptiaca* had low values (347 and 276 g/kg DM). Lignin (ADL) concentrations ranged from 141 g/kg DM in *B. aegyptiaca* to 237 g/kg DM in *G. senegalensis*. Regarding secondary compounds, TP concentrations ranged from 13 g/kg DM in *B. aegyptiaca* to 147 g/kg DM in *G. senegalensis*, while CT content was high in *K. senegalensis* (67 g/kg DM) and low in *B. aegyptiaca* (3 g/kg DM).

3.2. Effect of PEG on in vitro fermentation of selected tree leaves

In vitro GP, %CH₄, IVOMD and IVME showed pronounced interspecific differences as well as clear responses to PEG addition (Table 2). Kruskal–Wallis tests confirmed highly significant variation among species under both –PEG and +PEG conditions ($p < 0.001$). Post hoc Dunn tests indicated that *G. senegalensis* and *K. senegalensis* consistently yielded lower GP, IVOMD, and IVME values than *A. digitata* and *B. aegyptiaca* ($p < 0.05$). Similar patterns were observed for %CH₄, confirming that fermentation results were strongly species-dependent regardless of PEG treatment.

Under –PEG incubation conditions, the highest GP values were obtained for *A. digitata* (35.7 ml/200 mg DM) and *B. aegyptiaca* (31.8 ml/200 mg DM), and the lowest for *G. senegalensis* (8.8 ml/200 mg DM). PEG addition significantly increased GP in all

Table 1. Nutritional composition of five selected fodder tree leaves from the Sahelian zone of Senegal as determined from one pool sample per species across a number of individual trees.*

Species	DM [g/kg FM]	OM	CP	aNDF	ADF [g/kg DM]	ADL	TP	CT
<i>A. raddiana</i>	533	910	169	392	357	214	122	24
<i>A. digitata</i>	310	871	153	475	333	141	60	30
<i>B. aegyptiaca</i>	461	837	167	347	276	141	13	3
<i>G. senegalensis</i>	509	901	110	587	497	237	147	36
<i>K. senegalensis</i>	405	916	126	485	355	142	56	67

Note: DM, dry matter; FM, fresh matter; OM, organic matter; CP, crude protein; aNDF, amylase-free neutral detergent fibre; ADF, acid detergent fibre; ADL, acid detergent lignin; TP, Total phenols; CT, condensed tannins.

*Note: The $n = 1$ composite leaf sample per species was collected from 15, 5, 25, 18 and 9 trees, respectively, of *A. raddiana*, *A. digitata*, *B. aegyptiaca*, *G. senegalensis* and *K. senegalensis*. Each sample was analysed in duplicate to ensure analytical precision. No statistical tests were performed on this data.

Table 2. Effects of polyethylene glycol (PEG) addition (–/+ PEG) on *in vitro* gas production (GP), methane concentration in total gas (%CH₄), digestibility of organic matter (IVOMD), and metabolisable energy content (IVME) of five woody species from the Sahelian zone of Senegal. Values are means and standard deviation (±) of six syringes incubated in two runs per PEG (–/+) treatment.

Species, PEG	GP [ml/200 mg DM]	CH ₄ [% in GP]	IVOMD [%]	IVME [MJ/kg DM]
A. raddiana –	19.0 ^b ± 0.7	15.6 ± 1.7	47.5 ^b ± 0.6	8.7 ^b ± 0.1
A. raddiana +	35.1 ^a ± 0.8	18.8 ± 2.4	61.2 ^a ± 0.7	10.9 ^a ± 0.1
	***	ns	***	***
A. digitata –	35.7 ^b ± 1.2	16.5 ± 0.5	63.4 ^b ± 1.0	11.7 ^b ± 0.2
A. digitata +	39.2 ^a ± 0.6	15.6 ± 2.1	66.3 ^a ± 0.5	12.2 ^a ± 0.1
	*	ns	*	*
B. aegyptiaca –	31.8 ± 0.2	16.8 ± 0.3	63.2 ± 0.2	12.1 ± 0.0
B. aegyptiaca +	31.0 ± 0.3	17.8 ± 0.7	62.5 ± 0.3	12.0 ± 0.0
	ns	ns	ns	ns
G. senegalensis –	8.8 ^b ± 0.5	4.1 ^b ± 0.5	32.6 ^b ± 0.4	5.9 ^b ± 0.1
G. senegalensis +	16.9 ^a ± 0.6	9.3 ^a ± 0.9	39.5 ^a ± 0.5	6.9 ^a ± 0.1
	***	***	***	***
K. senegalensis –	21.3 ^b ± 0.6	9.6 ± 0.3	46.5 ^b ± 0.5	8.5 ^b ± 0.1
K. senegalensis +	33.3 ^a ± 0.4	11.9 ± 0.7	56.7 ^a ± 0.4	10.1 ^a ± 0.1
	***	ns	***	***

Note: Superscript letters (*a*, *b*) indicate significant differences between treatments (–PEG vs. +PEG) within each species (Wilcoxon paired test, $p < 0.05$). Significance levels: $p < 0.001$ (***); $p < 0.05$ (*); $p \geq 0.05$ (ns). For results of inter-species comparison please refer to the text (section 3.2).

species except *B. aegyptiaca* ($p < 0.001$), with the strongest response observed in *G. senegalensis* (+8.1 ml/200 mg DM). Methane concentration also varied significantly under –PEG conditions ($p < 0.01$), ranging from 4.1% in *G. senegalensis* to 16.8% in *B. aegyptiaca*. PEG addition led to a significant increase in %CH₄ for *G. senegalensis* and *K. senegalensis* ($p < 0.05$), indicating that CT in these species exerted an inhibitory effect on methanogenesis.

IVOMD followed similar interspecific trends, with *A. digitata* and *B. aegyptiaca* showing the highest values (around 63%), and *G. senegalensis* the lowest (32%) under –PEG conditions. PEG significantly increased IVOMD in most species, particularly in *G. senegalensis*, where digestibility increased by 6.9% units. IVME values showed corresponding improvements, from 8.7 to 10.9 MJ/kg DM in *A. raddiana*, and from 5.9 to 6.9 MJ/kg DM in *G. senegalensis* when PEG was added ($p < 0.001$ in both cases).

3.3. Preference and intake of fresh and dried leaves

3.3.1. Intake of leaves

During the adaptation and the transition period, behavioural observations (data not shown) confirmed that none of the sheep displayed positional preferences for specific bucket locations ($p > 0.05$). Average feeding time at each bucket position was also similar across the four animals, indicating that bucket position did not influence subsequent intake measurements. Significant differences ($p < 0.001$) were observed between the five woody species in terms of average leaf intake, both on a fresh matter (FM) and dry matter (DM) basis (Table 3). During the daily 30-min feeding sessions, the highest average voluntary intake per animal was recorded for *A. raddiana* (276.5 g FM/animal; 184.5 g DM/animal) and *B. aegyptiaca* (216.6 g FM/animal; 167.0 g DM/animal). When expressed relative to body weight, *A. raddiana* and *B. aegyptiaca* remained the most

Table 3. Mean voluntary intake of fresh and dried leaves from five Sahelian tree species in Senegal by sheep, expressed per animal and per kilogram of body weight (BW), during a daily 30-min free choice period. Values are means across four animals and 5 d per state of leaf.

Species	Fresh state		Dried state	
	FM [g/animal]	FM [g/kg BW]	DM [g/animal]	DM [g/kg BW]
<i>Acacia raddiana</i>	276.5 ^a	9.8 ^a	184.5 ^a	6.5 ^a
<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	216.6 ^b	7.7 ^b	167.0 ^b	5.9 ^b
<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	7.9 ^c	0.3 ^c	7.9 ^c	0.3 ^c
<i>Guiera senegalensis</i>	5.9 ^c	0.2 ^c	0.0 ^c	0.0 ^c
<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	2.4 ^c	0.1 ^c	0.7 ^c	0.0 ^c
SEM	59.83	2.12	42.46	1.49
<i>p</i> -Value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

Note: BW, body weight; DM, dry matter; FM, fresh matter; SEM, standard error of the mean. Different superscript letters (a, b, c) within a column indicate statistically significant differences between species (linear mixed-effects model including animal and day as random effects, followed by Tukey-adjusted pairwise comparisons, $p < 0.05$).

consumed species, reaching 9.8 g FM/kg BW and 6.5 g DM/kg BW for *A. raddiana*, and 7.7 g FM/kg BW and 5.9 g DM/kg BW for *B. aegyptiaca*.

In contrast, *A. digitata*, *G. senegalensis*, and *K. senegalensis* were consumed in much lower quantities. Intake of *A. digitata* remained below 0.5 g DM/kg BW, whereas consumption of *G. senegalensis* and *K. senegalensis* was nearly zero, indicating minimal voluntary intake of these species.

3.3.2. Feeding time

Significant differences in feeding time were observed between the five woody species ($p < 0.001$; Figure 2). In the fresh leaf trial, sheep spent the longest time feeding on *A.*

Figure 2. Ingestion time (seconds) of sheep for five fodder tree species offered in fresh (left) and dried (right) state. Species are *Adansonia digitata* (Ad), *Acacia tortilis* subsp. *raddiana* (Ac), *Balanites aegyptiaca* (Ba), *Guiera senegalensis* (Gu), and *Khaya senegalensis* (Kh). Black diamonds indicate the mean ingestion time for each species. Letters denote significant differences among species (linear mixed-effects model with estimated marginal means, Tukey adjustment, $p < 0.05$). Data were collected during a daily 30-min observation period over 5 d per leaf state.

Figure 3. Preference coefficient of sheep for five fodder tree species offered in fresh (left) and dried (right) state. Species are *Acacia tortilis* subsp. *raddiana* (Ac), *Adansonia digitata* (Ad), *Balanites aegyptiaca* (Ba), *Guiera senegalensis* (Gu), and *Khaya senegalensis* (Kh). Black diamonds indicate the mean preference coefficient for each species. Letters denote significant differences among species (linear mixed-effects model with estimated marginal means, Tukey adjustment, $p < 0.05$). Data were collected during a 30-min observation period over 5 d per leaf state. Please note the differing scales of the y-axes.

raddiana and *B. aegyptiaca*, with average durations exceeding 800 s during the 30-min observation period. In contrast, feeding times for *A. digitata*, *G. senegalensis*, and *K. senegalensis* remained below 100 s. A similar pattern was observed in the dried leaf trial, where *A. raddiana* and *B. aegyptiaca* again showed markedly longer feeding durations than the other species.

3.3.3. Preference coefficient

As shown in Figure 3, the PC revealed marked differences in sheep's preference for the five woody species ($p < 0.001$), both for fresh and dried leaves. In the fresh leaf trial, *A. raddiana* and *B. aegyptiaca* displayed significantly higher preference coefficients (PC > 0.5) compared with *A. digitata*, *G. senegalensis*, and *K. senegalensis*, all of which remained below 0.15. A similar pattern was observed for dried leaves, where *A. raddiana* and *B. aegyptiaca* maintained the highest PC values (around 0.6), while the remaining three species showed coefficients close to zero.

3.4. Relationship between forage quality, fermentability and animal preference

Associations were observed between forage quality traits and key animal (PC) and *in vitro* fermentation responses (GP and %CH₄), as shown in Figure 4. Given that only five tree species were studied, these correlations should be interpreted as exploratory and descriptive rather than inferential. CP was positively associated with PC and %CH₄, whereas aNDF showed negative association with both variables, and ADF was negatively related to GP. This suggests that higher fibre concentrations coincided with reduced leaf intake *in vivo* and with lower overall gas and methane production *in vitro*. As a result of how IVOMD was calculated (see 2.4.2.), this variable was positively associated with GP.

Figure 4. Pearson correlation coefficient heatmap between forage quality parameters (CP, aNDF, ADF, CT, TP, IVOMD), animal preference (Pref), and *in vitro* fermentation variables (GP, %CH₄). The colour intensity indicates the strength and direction of the correlation. Please note that, given the small number of tree species studied ($n = 5$), the correlations should be interpreted as indicative only, even though asterisks denote statistical significance. ADF, acid detergent fibre; aNDF, amylase-free neutral detergent fibre; %CH₄, methane concentration in *in vitro* GP; CP, crude protein; CT, condensed tannins; GP, *in vitro* gas production; IVOMD, *in vitro* organic matter digestibility; Pref, preference coefficient; TP, total phenols.

The CT concentration was negatively associated with PC and %CH₄, indicating that tannin-rich species were generally less preferred and yielded lower methane concentrations *in vitro*. In contrast, TP showed relatively weak associations with most response variables.

4. Discussion

4.1. Nutritional value of woody forage species

The five woody species evaluated in this study exhibited distinct nutritional profiles that highlight both their potential and their limitations as dry-season feed resources for ruminants in the Sahel. *A. raddiana* and *B. aegyptiaca* were characterised by relatively high crude protein concentrations and favourable *in vitro* organic matter digestibility, confirming their recognised forage value as reported in previous studies (Ammar et al. 2004; Becho 2016). These attributes make them particularly suitable for alleviating the protein deficits commonly encountered during the dry season in Sahelian livestock systems.

In contrast, *G. senegalensis* and *K. senegalensis* displayed lower nutritional potential, largely due to their elevated fibre fractions and high concentrations of condensed tannins. Earlier findings by Frutos et al. (2004) have shown that high tannin levels can inhibit rumen microbial activity, thereby reducing digestibility and voluntary intake. This is consistent with the poor performance of these two species in both the cafeteria-style trial and the *in vitro* fermentation assay.

Although *K. senegalensis* had a comparatively high CP concentration, its effective feeding value appeared to be markedly constrained by its secondary metabolite profile. Similar observations were made by Coulibaly et al. (2025) in Mali, where sheep exhibited very low intake of *K. senegalensis* leaves despite their considerable protein content. Such discrepancies between nutrient concentration and actual feeding value underscore the importance of considering both nutritive and antinutritive factors when evaluating the use of woody fodder species for ruminant diets.

4.2. Antinutritional effects of tannins

The comparison of *in vitro* incubations with and without PEG provided clear evidence of the biological activity of TP, and particularly CT, in the studied tree leaves. Although TP and CT concentrations were generally moderate, the significant increases in GP and %CH₄ following PEG addition highlight their functional relevance. This observation is consistent with the findings of Mlambo et al. (2007), who emphasised the usefulness of PEG as a diagnostic tool for assessing tannin activity by comparing its effects to those obtained with rumen fluid from tannin-adapted animals. In the present case, however, the donor of rumen fluid was not adapted to tannins, which underscores the diagnostic value of PEG also under non-adapted conditions.

The findings also support the claim of Getachew et al. (2000) and Frutos et al. (2004) that tannin effects are not solely determined by concentration, but also by their chemical structure and binding affinity.

Among the species evaluated, *G. senegalensis* and *K. senegalensis* showed the strongest response to PEG addition, reflecting the presence of bioactive tannins that substantially impair rumen microbial fermentation. This observation is consistent with Jones et al. (2001), who demonstrated the ability of PEG to neutralise tannins, as well as with Salem et al. (2005), who reported improved digestibility of tannin-rich forages when PEG was applied. Overall, PEG addition reduced the magnitude of interspecific variation in *in vitro* variables but did not modify the ranking of species in terms of fermentation performance. *A. digitata* and *B. aegyptiaca* consistently exhibited the highest fermentability and energy values, while *G. senegalensis* remained the least fermentable species. These results indicate that the chemical composition of the leaves, in particular tannin concentration and reactivity, plays a more decisive role in determining fermentation efficiency than PEG responsiveness alone.

The PEG-induced increase in %CH₄, particularly marked in *G. senegalensis*, aligns with the findings of Jayanegara et al. (2012) who highlighted the dual role of tannins in simultaneously limiting digestibility and suppressing methanogenesis. Such dual functionality underscores the complexity of tannin-microbe interactions and the need to assess both benefits and constraints when evaluating woody fodder species.

From a practical perspective, *A. raddiana* and *B. aegyptiaca* emerged as the most promising woody fodder species. Their favourable CP content, relatively high IVOMD and comparatively low %CH₄ results even in the absence of PEG suggest that they may support improved animal performance while contributing to reduced enteric methane output when included in dry-season diets of Sahelian ruminants.

4.3. Interplay between woody forage composition, fermentation, and intake by sheep

Overall, the animal response variables feeding time, dry matter intake, and preference coefficient, as determined during 30-min testing periods, showed patterns that were associated with key forage quality parameters, particularly CP, aNDF, ADF, CT and IVOMD. However, the limited number of only five ligneous species warrants cautious interpretation of the results obtained through Pearson correlation analysis. Still, the results indicate that ruminants respond sensitively to the nutritional and biochemical characteristics of woody foliage, both in terms of feeding behaviour and voluntary intake. This behavioural regulation aligns with the framework described by Provenza et al. (2003), who demonstrated that ruminants adjust intake according to the nutritional value, sensory attributes, and post-ingestive feedback associated with feeds. More recently, Widodo et al. (2023) similarly highlighted the close relationships between leaf chemical composition and digestibility under tropical conditions.

In the present study, protein-rich species such as *A. raddiana* and *B. aegyptiaca* were the most preferred and most consumed, whereas species with higher fibre and tannin concentrations, including *G. senegalensis* and *K. senegalensis*, exhibited markedly lower intake. Nevertheless, the observed preferences reflect short-term feeding behaviour under controlled conditions rather than long-term dietary selection of sheep under practical grazing or supplementation management.

The inverse relationship between the leaves' fibre content and palatability is consistent with Souza et al. (2010), who reported that structural carbohydrates limited intake through their bulk, reduced degradability, and slowed rumen passage. Gninkplékpo et al. (2024) reported that sheep in semi-arid Benin consumed more of the woody species with higher digestibility, but although *A. digitata* exhibited relatively high IVOMD values, its poor intake suggests that other factors – possibly organoleptic attributes or defensive traits such as latex exudation or bitter taste – may have deterred consumption, as previously documented by Abdulrazak et al. (2000).

Similarly, Gaviria-Urbe et al. (2020) reported that supplementing tropical grass-based diets with leguminous shrub leaves improved digestibility, voluntary intake, and fermentation outcomes in goats, highlighting the broader relevance of shrub foliage in small ruminant nutrition. In the present study, the positive association between the leaves' CP content with *in vitro* %CH₄ should be regarded as indicative only given the limited number of observations. Protein-rich tree foliage may enhance fermentative activity in the rumen, which can lead to higher methane production. However, this relationship is not universal. As emphasised by Verma et al. (2024), high digestibility does not necessarily translate into elevated methane emissions, especially when feeds contain fermentation-modulating secondary compounds.

The concentration of CT showed a negative association with both *in vitro* %CH₄ and the preference coefficient, which again applies only to the context of the five ligneous species. Tannins at moderate concentrations may reduce methanogenesis, whereas high levels tend to depress intake and nutrient utilisation (Aboagye and Beauchemin 2019). The contrasting effects of CT observed for different woody species in this study's behavioural component (intake and preference) and *in vitro* testing (PEG-modulated GP and %CH₄) thus point to their dual role as both antinutritive and potential methane-mitigating agents.

Taken together, the present findings support the strategic value of local fodder trees for designing more sustainable feeding systems in the West African silvopastoral zone. As highlighted by Pamo et al. (2007), selecting fodder species according to their chemical and functional properties offers an effective means of improving animal performance and can at the same time also reduce the environmental footprint of ruminant production.

5. Conclusion

In the Sahelian silvopastoral zone of Senegal, sheep exhibited clear feeding preferences for the leaves of *Acacia tortilis* subsp. *raddiana* and *Balanites aegyptiaca*, which were characterised by high crude protein content and favourable *in vitro* digestibility. In contrast, leaves of *Guiera senegalensis* and *Khaya senegalensis* were minimally consumed and showed comparatively low *in vitro* digestibility, largely due to their high concentrations of condensed tannins and structural fibre. Although *Adansonia digitata* displayed relatively high *in vitro* digestibility, its poor palatability suggests the influence of organoleptic or defensive compounds that limited its intake by sheep.

The inhibitory effects of condensed tannins on *in vitro* fermentation were confirmed by the response to polyethylene glycol; however, PEG supplementation is not a practical option in extensive Sahelian livestock systems. Overall, the combined evidence from the cafeteria-style trial and the laboratory analyses of the five selected tree species aligns well with local knowledge regarding high-potential indigenous fodder trees. Promoting the use and sustainable management of such species offers a promising strategy to improve dry-season nutrition of small ruminants and could potentially contribute to methane mitigation. However, the extent to which the latter *in vitro* observation translates into reduced methane emissions under practical feeding conditions needs to be verified through *in vivo* studies.

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Author contributions

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Data availability statement

For scientific purposes, the data presented in this study will be made available upon request to the corresponding author, without undue reservation.

Institutional review board statement

The animal study protocol was approved by the Senegalese Institute of Agricultural Research (ISRA), Senegal, under the authority of the Ethics Committee for Animal Research (approval date and number: 24-February-2022). All procedures involving animals were conducted in accordance with institutional and national guidelines for the care and use of animals in research.

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